

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE CRITICAL REVIEW OF CAREER APPROACHES AND THEORIES

Huseynli Chinara Aydin

Phd student of Baku State University

Department of Social Psychology

Baku 1148, Z.Khalilov street 23

Abstract

A properly structured model of career guidance organization maps out the best career choice in advance in a logical sequence to prepare the young generation for successful and professional activity, develops that career according to its parameters, and creates the opportunity to achieve optimal results. Career guidance is a joint work of the school, family, and the student himself, and students who are guided in organizing this work are able to make decisions faster than their peers. Parents and teachers should also support students in making choices in accordance with their interests, talents, and values when guiding them to choose a career. Helping teenagers choose their own path logically will contribute to their personal development and successful adaptation to a changing world. An incorrectly chosen career has a significant impact on the psychological state, personal development, and social environment of the student, leading to failure in their career.

The main aim of the study is presenting comparative review about different career approaches in modern psychology.

Keywords: career guidance, self-determination, personality, educational environment.

Professional self-determination of a person is a social process, the main content of which is connected with a person's choice of his profession. Choice is an important stage of self-determination of a person and is a psychological "check" of the requirements of the profession by the individual, an assessment of his objective capabilities in the implementation of specific types of activity, and whether the value-motivational sphere of the personality corresponds to the requirements of the social environment.

Vocational orientation and choice of profession are always a decisive moment in human life, requiring the resolution of a whole complex of contradictions, primarily desirable and necessary for the individual and society. In a choice situation, the prestige and attractiveness of the profession are one of the factors determining the behavior of the subject. These are also social mechanisms for regulating the professional mobility of the personality.

It should be noted that, although the attractiveness and prestige of the profession have similar features, they have different properties in terms of content. If the assessment of the attractiveness of a profession is always subjective and more often expresses the interests, values, and attitudes of the individual, then the prestige of the profession manifests itself in his consciousness as a reflection of a positive public assessment. It is known that the term "vocational orientation" first entered everyday life in the United States at the beginning of the last century. Over the following years, vocational orientation has been developed and studied by various researchers. In modern times, since properly organized vocational orientation work among people is the key to the successful personnel policy of the state, its study is of particular relevance. It should be noted that although numerous research works have been devoted to the study of the problem of vocational orientation, the results obtained in this area have not been sufficiently systematized.

Before proceeding directly to the analysis of scientific approaches to vocational orientation, it is necessary to consider the definitions of vocational orientation available in the scientific literature.

According to S. N. Chistyakov, vocational orientation can be considered as "a scientific and practical system of preparing students for a free, conscious choice of profession". According to another researcher S. Y. Batshev, vocational orientation is a purposeful activity associated with the formation of professional interests and inclinations of the growing generation in accordance with their personal abilities, the requirements of society and their suitability for this or that profession.

In psychology, vocational orientation is analyzed as two mutual psychological processes: the decision-making by a person about his choice of profession and its impact on the human psyche in order to form professional intentions in it. In sociological and economic studies, "vocational orientation is considered as a set of socio-economic relations between society and its members on the issue of the formation of a specialized workforce, taking into account social needs [4, p. 62].

The prominent researcher V. D. Simonenko explains such diversity and variety in vocational orientation by the fact that vocational orientation is pedagogical in terms of work methods, social in terms of content, economic in terms of results, and state in terms of organization. T. E. Dus, who conducted research in this direction, put forward the following classification of scientific approaches to the study of vocational orientation: pedagogical, psychological, sociological, economic, medical-biological, managerial-organizational, and approaches related to the legal regulation of vocational orientation. Let us try to analyze the approaches we have mentioned.

Among these approaches, the pedagogical approach is considered to be an earlier approach in terms of the date of its formation. Within the framework of

this approach, various forms and methods of vocational orientation training and education are studied. The issues of introducing students to socially useful labor, educational and extracurricular work with the main professional groups are considered. The upbringing of diligence, respectful attitude to professional labor, as well as the professional formation of personality is of great importance. The main institution of social vocational orientation that practices this approach is undoubtedly secondary educational institutions. It should be noted that the pedagogical approach to the study of vocational orientation is closely related to the psychological approach [4, p. 51]. The psychological aspect of vocational orientation is more devoted to the study of internal and external psychological factors that influence the choice of profession. This includes issues of psychological preparation for labor activity, psychological characteristics of the personality (interests, inclinations, abilities, needs, requirements, etc.), value orientations that contribute to the formation of vocational orientation, and motivation issues. In fact, when talking about vocational orientation, it is impossible to reveal the content of the concept without clarifying the psychological side of this process.

All processes taking place in society directly or indirectly affect the vocational self-determination of students. Vocational self-determination is one of the integral components of the process of socialization of the personality. Within the framework of the sociological approach, social factors that influence the choice of profession, public demand for personnel, and the labor market are studied.

The economic side of the study of vocational guidance is quite close to the sociological approach. The tasks of this approach are to solve the problem of training qualified personnel for various sectors of industry, agriculture, service sectors, etc. Special attention is paid to the requirements of various sectors of production. Within the framework of vocational guidance, a relatively new direction in socio-economic approach vocational guidance, vocational adaptation, which consists in modeling real working conditions or life situations related to future professional activity, also occupies one of the main places. Within the framework of sociological and economic approaches, the main institution of social vocational guidance is the employment centers of the population.

Another approach to vocational guidance is the medical-biological approach. Supporters of this approach pay special attention to taking into account medical contraindications and the physiological foundations of the success of professional work when choosing a particular profession. It is noted that the advice given by a doctor on a profession should be implemented before all other advice. In this case, the work of medical-social expertise and rehabilitation centers, such as the institute of social vocational guidance, is of particular importance.

The management-organizational approach to vocational guidance is associated with the study of the problems of organizing its administrative management. Within the framework of this approach, the basic rules,

goals, requirements and procedure for conducting vocational guidance work are considered. Scientific management of vocational guidance reflects the collection and processing of information, the preparation of a program of actions, control, and a set of recommendations. Legal management of vocational guidance, which considers the legal issues of organizing vocational guidance work and is aimed at the legal regulation of socio-economic relations, and determines modern directions in vocational guidance, is close to the management-organizational approach. It seems that the state, which determines the state policy and development strategy of vocational guidance activities, is engaged in management - organizational activities and legal management of vocational guidance [3, p.34].

From the analysis of the studies conducted on the study of vocational guidance, it becomes clear that it is necessary to pay attention to the study of this problem within the framework of an interdisciplinary approach. The content of the interdisciplinary approach consists of a combination and interaction of all the approaches described above. Within the framework of this approach, taking into account the above, the following definition of vocational guidance is proposed: "vocational guidance is a purposeful, state-organized and regulated activity that includes the study of the labor market and public demand for personnel, as well as the study of the psychological and physiological characteristics of persons choosing a profession and the provision of pedagogical and psychological assistance to them in choosing a profession". According to most researchers, the most important social vocational guidance institution is the school, where a greater number of young people choosing a profession are trained.

It should be noted that the most widespread of the scientific approaches to the organization of vocational guidance in educational institutions is the system-functional approach. This approach involves the involvement of the entire pedagogical staff of the school in vocational guidance work. In this case, the main responsibility for the correct guidance of vocational guidance falls on the teacher-psychologist and social pedagogue (vocational counselors). They organize and coordinate the work of class leaders, subject teachers and medical workers. The vocational guidance process is led by the deputy director of the school for educational and ideological work. The "legislative body" of vocational guidance is the school's vocational guidance council, which develops the vocational guidance strategy, approves the work plan and exercises control. The council includes the school director, deputy director for educational and ideological work, vocational counselors, class leaders of two or three classes and representatives of the school's parent committee. The participation of parents in vocational guidance work is an integral pedagogical condition for the effectiveness of vocational guidance. The personality-oriented approach to the organization of vocational guidance, according to N. P. Burnatov, consists in cooperating with teachers when providing assistance to students in choosing a profession in accordance with the individual characteristics of the personality and the needs of the labor market, and

in activating the initiative of schoolchildren in the process of professional self-determination [5, p. 46]. In this approach, the organization of assistance in vocational guidance is carried out through the accompaniment, support, interaction of teachers, assistance in solving problems of professional self-determination, the creation of favorable conditions, a pedagogical environment [4, p. 12]. The personality-oriented approach to the organization of vocational guidance, unlike the approach of the same name to its content, is, in our opinion, optimal, since it completely fits into the framework of the general humanistic approach to education. Examples of approaches to the organization of vocational guidance are also educational, diagnostic and educational approaches. It should be noted that these approaches are not clearly delimited, they often overlap, but nevertheless it is very important to distinguish them [6]. In the educational approach, the main attention is paid to the professional enlightenment of the professional orientation. That is, the pedagogical impact on the personality is minimized and limited to acquaintance with the professional world. The diagnostic approach to professional orientation began to be applied thanks to the development of experimental pedagogy and psychology, testology. Tests are short-term standardized tests of personality traits. Unlike the educational approach, in this approach, work with personality comes first and is carried out within the framework of professional counseling. The educational approach is associated with the implementation of the main function of the educator - the formation of intelligence, character, feelings, will, skills [4, p. 65]. The educational approach is considered from the perspective of professional orientation as the development of important professional qualities (VPK) in the personality and contributes to the process of professional adaptation. A comprehensive approach to the organization of professional orientation involves the constant, uninterrupted use of all three approaches.

It should be noted that the differentiated approach is associated with the distribution of students into groups depending on their psychological characteristics for the purpose of conducting vocational guidance activities. There are several types of differentiated approaches. For example, the gender approach, in which the optants are divided into groups according to sexual characteristics. The existence of this approach is explained by the variety of forms, methods, techniques, and means of vocational guidance used in any particular situation, as well as some differences in the psyche

of boys and girls. In this case, the age characteristics of the optants are taken into account. The content of vocational guidance activities and their organization vary depending on the age of the students. As a vivid example of the differentiated approach, we can cite the experience of using the classification of professions by Y. A. Klimov, who distinguished five types of professions according to the criteria of the requirements of important professional qualities: "Human - human", "Human - system of signs", "Human - nature", "Human - technique", "Human - artistic image". Groups are formed based on the tendency of the optants to one or another type of profession. Although it requires extensive initial preparation for the organization of vocational orientation, a differentiated approach is of great importance. The content of the differential approach is of great importance both for the activation of the optant's professional self-determination and for the correction of the pedagogical effect. The main advantage of this approach is the presence of certain rules that guarantee the equal positions of the interviewees and the absence of noticeable psychological "pressure" on the optant.

Source of Funding: None.

The research was realized at Baku State University, Faculty of Social science and psychology.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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